

Syntheses and characterization of coordination compounds of monobasic bidentate (NS donor) Schiff bases derived from aldehydopolystyrene and 2-aminoethanethiol or 2-aminothiophenol

D. Kumar*, A. Syamal** and A. K. Singh

Department of Chemistry, National Institute of Technology, Kurukshetra-136 119, India

E-mail : anand_reck@yahoo.com Fax : 91-1744-238050

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Aldehydopolystyrene reacts with 2-aminoethanethiol or 2-aminothiophenol in 1 : 4.68 molar ratio to form polystyrene-anchored Schiff bases, PS-LH (1) or PS-L'H (2) respectively. PS-LH or PS-L'H reacts with metal salts in DMF to form the polystyrene-anchored coordination compounds, [PS-LM(CH₃COO)·DMF] (where M = Cu, Zn, Cd, UO₂), [PS-LM'(CH₃COO)·3DMF] (where M' = Co, Ni), [PS-LFeCl₂·2DMF] and [PS-LMoO₂(acac)] (where acacH = acetylacetonone). PS-L'H also forms the similar types of compounds. The polystyrene-anchored coordination compounds have been characterized on the basis of elemental analyses, IR, reflectance spectral and magnetic susceptibility measurements. The shifts of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ (azomethine), $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$ (thioalcoholic) or $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$ (thiophenolic) stretches of 1 or 2 in coordination compounds indicate their monobasic bidentate (NS donor) behaviour. The polystyrene-anchored Co^{II}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Fe^{III} compounds are paramagnetic, while others are diamagnetic. The Cd^{II} and Zn^{II} compounds are tetrahedral, Cu^{II} compounds are square planar, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Fe^{III}, MoO₂^{VI} and UO₂^{VI} compounds are octahedral. All the polystyrene-anchored coordination compounds are magnetically dilute in nature.

Anchoring chelating ligands to insoluble polymer supports and the reaction of these chelating resins with metal ions provide an easy route for the synthesis of immobilized transition metal compounds^{1,2}. Anchoring of few ligands containing NS donor atoms like thiosemicarbazide, 8-thioquinoline and cysteine to polymer matrix and their use in the metal ion separation are well known^{3,4}. The study of these immobilized chelating resins and their coordination compounds are limited to leaching of the metal ions from the polymer⁵. The study of coordination compounds of sulphur donor Schiff bases is of biochemical interest due to their carcinostatic (anticancer)⁶, antibacterial⁷ and antifungal⁸ activities. Sulphur donor compounds are expected to be the most effective anticancer agents as they usually confer lipid solubility on the metal complex. Sulphur donor Schiff bases have also been widely used as PVC-stabilizer⁹, agrochemicals and antifouling paints due to their low phototoxicity and favourable environmental degradation¹⁰. In this paper, the synthesis of two new polystyrene-anchored Schiff bases, PS-LH (1) and PS-L'H (2) and their coordination compounds with Cd^{II}, Co^{II}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Fe^{III}, MoO₂^{VI} and UO₂^{VI} ions are reported.

Results and discussion

The polystyrene-anchored Schiff bases (PS-LH) (1) and (PS-L'H) (2) were synthesized by the reaction of aldehydopolystyrene and 2-aminoethanethiol or 2-aminothiophenol in DMF as shown below :

Scheme 1. Preparative method of polystyrene-anchored Schiff bases.

The coupling reaction between PS-CHO and amines (in 1 : 4.68 molar ratio) in DMF leads to 100% conversion of

**Present address : D708, Ushanagar, Bhandup, Mumbai-400 078, India.

PS-CHO to produce **1** and **2**. The elemental analyses and IR spectral studies of polystyrene-anchored Schiff bases (**1** and **2**) also indicate the 100% conversion of PS-CHO to give **1** and **2**. The polystyrene-anchored Schiff bases (**1** and **2**) are insoluble in water, common coordinating and non-coordinating solvents. DMF is a convenient solvent for studying the metal loading property of **1** and **2**, due to its high dielectric constant and ability to swell the polystyrene support and to dissolve a large number of metal salts. The coordination compounds of **1** and **2** have been prepared by reacting **1** or **2** with appropriate metal salts in 1 : 2 molar ratio. The formation of polystyrene-anchored coordination compounds is given below by taking the representative case of PS-LH :

As the reaction of polystyrene-anchored Schiff bases (**1** and **2**) with metal salts proceeds, the colour of **1** and **2**

changes from cream to brown, yellow, red, dark-brown, green and pale-yellow, however, no appreciable change in colour is found in case of cadmium(II) and zinc(II) compounds from the starting resin (Table 1). The colours of polystyrene-anchored compounds do not change even after prolonged washings with DMF, methanol, ethanol and petroleum ether. The percent reaction conversion of polystyrene-anchored ligand to polystyrene-anchored compounds lies in the range : 47.6–95.5 and 35.0–98.4 for **1** and **2** respectively (Table 1). The metal binding capacity of **1** and **2** varies from 0.42–0.81 and 0.26–0.85 mmol of metal per g of **1** and **2** respectively. The polystyrene-anchored compounds lose the coordinated DMF completely on heating in air.

The IR spectral data of **1** and **2** and their coordination compounds are presented in Table 2. The aldehydo-polystyrene (PS-CHO) exhibits an IR band at 1685 cm⁻¹ due to ν(C=O) (aldehyde)³. This band disappears in **1** or **2** indicating 100% conversion of PS-CHO to **1** and **2**. The polystyrene-anchored Schiff bases (**1** and **2**) show a medium intense IR band at 2530 and 2510 cm⁻¹ respectively due to ν(S–H) stretch^{11,12}. The disappearance of this band in the respective coordination compounds indicates the deprotonation of thiol group and consequent coordination of sulphur atom to metal ions^{11,12}. PS-LH (**1**) exhibits bands at 1640 and 750 cm⁻¹ due to ν(C=N) (azomethine) and ν(C–S) (thioalcoholic) stretches, respectively. These bands undergo a negative shift of 10–20 and 90–110 cm⁻¹ respectively in the polystyrene-anchored compounds indicating the nitrogen and sulphur coordination respectively of **1** to metal ions. The Schiff base derived from salicylaldehyde and 2-aminoethanethiol exhibits ν(C=N) (azomethine) and ν(C–S) (thioalcoholic) stretches at 1650 and 755 cm⁻¹ respectively¹¹. In the zirconium(IV) and dioxouranium(VI) compounds of this Schiff base, the ν(C=N) (azomethine)

Table 1. Colour, analytical, metal binding capacity and percent reaction conversion data of polystyrene-anchored compounds

Compd.	Colour	Found (calcd.) (%)			Metal binding capacity (mmol/g of resin) ^a	Percent reaction conversion
		M	S	DMF		
PS-LH (1)	Cream	–	3.5 (3.58)	–	–	100
[PS-LCu(CH ₃ COO)·DMF]	Green	4.9 (5.72)	3.1 (2.88)	5.6 (6.58)	0.77	85.7
[PS-LZn(CH ₃ COO)·DMF]	Cream	3.2 (5.90)	2.9 (2.88)	3.6 (6.57)	0.49	54.2
[PS-LCd(CH ₃ COO)·DMF]	White	7.6 (9.70)	2.6 (2.76)	4.9 (6.30)	0.68	78.4
[PS-LUO ₂ (CH ₃ COO)·DMF]	Yellow	11.2 (18.10)	2.6 (2.43)	3.4 (5.50)	0.47	61.9
[PS-LFeCl ₂ ·2DMF]	Red	4.5 (4.71)	2.9 (2.70)	11.7 (12.3)	0.81	95.5
[PS-LCo(CH ₃ COO)·3DMF]	Brown	4.4 (4.71)	2.5 (2.56)	16.3 (17.50)	0.75	93.4
[PS-LNi(CH ₃ COO)·3DMF]	Green	3.4 (4.70)	2.8 (2.56)	12.6 (17.50)	0.58	72.3
[PS-LMoO ₂ (acac)]	Pale-yellow	4.0 (8.41)	2.5 (2.80)	–	0.42	47.6

Table-1 (contd.)

PS-L'H (2)	Cream	–	3.3 (3.35)	–	–	100
[PS-L'Cu(CH ₃ COO)·DMF]	Brown	5.4 (5.49)	2.9 (2.76)	6.2 (6.30)	0.85	98.4
[PS-L'Zn(CH ₃ COO)·DMF]	Cream	4.3 (5.64)	2.8 (2.76)	4.8 (6.30)	0.66	76.2
[PS-L'Cd(CH ₃ COO)·DMF]	Cream	5.1 (9.33)	2.8 (2.66)	3.3 (6.06)	0.45	54.7
[PS-L'UO ₂ (CH ₃ COO)·DMF]	Yellow	6.1 (17.40)	2.2 (2.34)	1.9 (5.34)	0.26	35.0
[PS-L'FeCl ₂ ·2DMF]	Red	4.0 (4.54)	2.8 (2.60)	10.5 (11.86)	0.72	88.1
[PS-L'Co(CH ₃ COO)·3DMF]	Dark-brown	2.4 (4.54)	2.4 (2.46)	8.9 (16.86)	0.41	52.9
[PS-L'Ni(CH ₃ COO)·3DMF]	Green	1.8 (4.52)	2.5 (2.46)	6.7 (16.86)	0.31	39.8
[PS-L'MoO ₂ (acac)]	Yellow	7.4 (8.08)	2.7 (2.69)	–	0.77	91.6

^aMetal binding capacity = [M% (observed) × 10]/(atomic weight of metal).

Table 2. Infrared, reflectance spectral data (cm⁻¹) and magnetic susceptibility measurements of polystyrene-anchored ligands and their compounds

Compd.	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ (azomethine)	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$ (thioalcoholic)/ (thiophenolic)	ν_{max} (cm ⁻¹)	χ_{dia} (10 ⁻⁶ cgs units)	$\chi_{\text{M}}^{\text{corr}}$ (10 ⁻⁶ cgs units)	Magnetic moment ^a (B.M.) [Temp.] (K)
PS-LH (1)	1640	750				
[PS-LCu(CH ₃ COO)·DMF]	1625	650	17850	-811	1598	1.91 [285]
[PS-LZn(CH ₃ COO)·DMF]	1630	655				
[PS-LCd(CH ₃ COO)·DMF]	1630	640				
[PS-LUO ₂ (CH ₃ COO)·DMF]	1625	655				
[PS-LFeCl ₂ ·2DMF]	1620	640	12500 18300 25000	-795	15244	5.92 [287]
[PS-LCo(CH ₃ COO)·3DMF]	1630	650	8620 20000	-841	11197	5.07 [287]
[PS-LNi(CH ₃ COO)·3DMF]	1620	660	8270 15050 25000	-1037	4090	3.05 [285]
[PS-LMoO ₂ (acac)]	1620	645				
PS-L'H (2)	1650	780				
[PS-L'Cu(CH ₃ COO)·DMF]	1620	840	16800	-741	1561	1.95 [305]
[PS-L'Zn(CH ₃ COO)·DMF]	1620	815				
[PS-L'Cd(CH ₃ COO)·DMF]	1615	820				
[PS-L'UO ₂ (CH ₃ COO)·DMF]	1630	815				
[PS-L'FeCl ₂ ·2DMF]	1625	830	12800 19650 23800	-876	14303	5.86 [300]
[PS-L'Co(CH ₃ COO)·3DMF]	1610	830	10000 20600	-1419	10438	5.03 [306]
[PS-L'Ni(CH ₃ COO)·3DMF]	1630	820	9880 16670 25640	-1794	3851	3.07 [306]
[PS-L'MoO ₂ (acac)]	1610	825				

^a $\mu_{\text{eff.}} = 2.83 (\chi_{\text{M}}^{\text{corr}} \times T)^{1/2}$ B.M.

and $\nu(\text{C-S})$ (thioalcoholic) stretches also undergo a negative shifts of 10–15 and 80–115 cm^{-1} respectively¹¹. PS-L'H (**2**) exhibits bands at 1650 and 780 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{C=N})$ (azomethine) and $\nu(\text{C-S})$ (thiophenolic) stretches respectively. In the polystyrene-anchored coordination compounds of **2**, the $\nu(\text{C=N})$ (azomethine) stretch undergoes a negative shift of 20–40 cm^{-1} and $\nu(\text{C-S})$ (thiophenolic) stretch to a positive shift of 35–60 cm^{-1} indicating the nitrogen and sulphur coordination respectively of **2** to metal ions. The Schiff base derived from salicylaldehyde and 3-aminothiophenol exhibits $\nu(\text{C=N})$ (azomethine) and $\nu(\text{C-S})$ (thiophenolic) stretches at 1645 and 755 cm^{-1} respectively¹². In the zirconium(IV) and dioxouranium(VI) compounds of this Schiff base, the $\nu(\text{C=N})$ (azomethine) stretch undergoes a negative shift of 20–30 cm^{-1} and $\nu(\text{C-S})$ (thiophenolic) stretch to a positive shift of 40–65 cm^{-1} respectively¹². Thus, the IR data are indicative of monobasic bidentate NS donor behaviour of **1** and **2**. The $\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{CO}_2)$ and $\nu_{\text{sy}}(\text{CO}_2)$ stretches of free acetate ions are found at 1560 and 1416 cm^{-1} respectively^{13,14}. The $\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{CO}_2)$ and $\nu_{\text{sy}}(\text{CO}_2)$ bands in the polystyrene-anchored acetate compounds occur in the range : 1580–1610 and 1360–1390 cm^{-1} respectively. The energy separation ($\Delta\nu = 190\text{--}250 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) between $\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{CO}_2)$ and $\nu_{\text{sy}}(\text{CO}_2)$ is greater than 144 cm^{-1} and this indicates the monodentate nature of acetate ion since in the event of bidentate coordination^{13,14}, the energy separation between $\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{CO}_2)$ and $\nu_{\text{sy}}(\text{CO}_2)$ is less than 144 cm^{-1} . DMF exhibits a band at 1680 cm^{-1} due to the $\nu(\text{C=O})$ stretch and this band shifts to lower energy by 10–40 cm^{-1} in the polystyrene-anchored compounds of **1** and **2** indicating the oxygen coordination of DMF to metal ions¹⁵. The polystyrene-anchored iron(III) compounds do not exhibit any new band at 820–860 cm^{-1} due to $\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{Fe-O-Fe})$ stretch and this precludes the presence of an oxo-bridged structure in the iron(III) compounds. The polystyrene-anchored dioxomolybdenum(VI) compounds exhibit two bands in the region : 930–960 cm^{-1} and 850–865 cm^{-1} due to the $\nu_{\text{sy}}(\text{O=Mo=O})$ and $\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{O=Mo=O})$ stretches respectively; the reported ranges for $\nu_{\text{sy}}(\text{O=Mo=O})$ and $\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{O=Mo=O})$ stretches for the majority of dioxomolybdenum(VI) compounds being 892–964 cm^{-1} and 840–925 cm^{-1} respectively¹⁶. The IR data are indicative of the presence of a *cis*- MoO_2 structure as a compound with a *trans*- MoO_2 structure, is expected to show only the $\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{O=Mo=O})$ band since the $\nu_{\text{sy}}(\text{O=Mo=O})$ is IR inactive. The *cis*- MoO_2 structure forces the ligand to coordinate in a non-planar fashion¹⁷. The absence of a band at $\sim 770 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the polystyrene-anchored dioxomolybdenum(VI) compounds indicate the absence of an oligometric structure with $\cdots\text{Mo=O}\cdots\text{Mo=O}\cdots$ interaction¹⁶. The polystyrene-anchored dioxouranium(VI)

compounds exhibit the $\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{O=U=O})$ stretch at 900–915 cm^{-1} which is in the usual range (870–950 cm^{-1}) observed for the majority of dioxouranium(VI) compounds¹⁸. The observation of only one $\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{O=U=O})$ band is indicative of the *trans*- UO_2 structure, since $\nu_{\text{sy}}(\text{O=U=O})$ is IR inactive.

The room temperature magnetic susceptibilities and magnetic moments of the compounds are given in Table 2. The polystyrene-anchored copper(II) compounds exhibit the magnetic moments in the range : 1.91–1.95 B.M. and fall in the usual range (1.75–2.2 B.M.) reported for magnetically dilute square planar copper(II) compounds¹⁵. The polystyrene-anchored cobalt(II) compounds exhibit the magnetic moments in the range : 5.03–5.07 B.M. which are close to the normal range (4.70–5.30 B.M.) expected for magnetically dilute octahedral cobalt(II) compounds¹⁵. The polystyrene-anchored nickel(II) compounds exhibit the magnetic moments in the range : 3.05–3.07 B.M. which fall in the range (2.9–3.4 B.M.) reported for magnetically dilute octahedral nickel(II) compounds¹⁵. The polystyrene-supported iron(III) compounds exhibit the magnetic moments in the range : 5.86–5.92 B.M. which are close to the normal range (5.8–6.0 B.M.) expected for high spin and magnetically dilute octahedral iron(III) compounds¹⁵. The polystyrene-anchored zinc(II), cadmium(II), dioxouranium(VI) and dioxomolybdenum(VI) compounds are diamagnetic as expected. A tetrahedral structure for zinc(II) and cadmium(II) compounds; a square planar structure for copper(II) compounds; and an octahedral structure for cobalt(II), nickel(II), iron(III), dioxomolybdenum(VI) and dioxouranium(VI) compounds are suggested. The magnetic data are consistent with the magnetically dilute nature of the compounds. The dimer formation, which leads to the antiferromagnetic exchange, is blocked in the present polystyrene-anchored compounds due to large framework of the polystyrene backbone and long distance between two adjacent metal centres.

The electronic spectra of the compounds could not be recorded in nujol mull as the compounds do not form a good mull. Hence, the reflectance spectra of the compounds were recorded (Table 2). The polystyrene-anchored copper(II) compounds exhibit one asymmetric broad band at 16800–17850 cm^{-1} which is assigned to the ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$, ${}^2B_{2g}$ and 2E_g transitions, characteristic of square planar geometry¹⁹. The absence of a band in the range : 8000–10000 cm^{-1} precludes the presence of a tetrahedral structure²⁰. The polystyrene-anchored cobalt(II) compounds exhibit two bands in the range : 8620–10000 and 20000–20600 cm^{-1} due to the ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(v_1)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)(v_3)$ transitions, respectively in an octahedral symmetry²¹. The $v_3 : v_1$ value for the present cobalt(II) compounds are 2.06 and 2.32 respectively and lies in the usual

range (2.0–2.80) reported for the majority of octahedral cobalt(II) compounds²¹. The spectral parameters²¹ are : $D_q = 978$ and 1122 cm^{-1} , $B' = 836$ and 788 cm^{-1} , $\beta = 0.86$ and 0.81 and $\beta^0 = 14$ and 19% . The reduction of the Racah parameter (B) from the free ion value of 971 cm^{-1} to 836 or 788 cm^{-1} and the β^0 value of 14 and 19% suggest the covalent nature of the cobalt(II) compounds. The polystyrene-anchored nickel(II) compounds exhibit three bands in the region : $8270\text{--}9880$, $15050\text{--}16670$ and $25000\text{--}25640 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to the spin-allowed transitions, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(v_1)$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)(v_2)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)(v_3)$ respectively, in an octahedral symmetry²¹. The $v_2 : v_1$ value for the present nickel(II) compounds are 1.69 and 1.82 respectively and lies in the range ($1.60\text{--}1.82$) reported for the majority of octahedral nickel(II) compounds²². The spectral parameters²¹ of the nickel(II) compounds are : $D_q = 827$ and 988 cm^{-1} , $B' = 933$ and 786 cm^{-1} , $\beta = 0.88$ and 0.74 , $\beta^0 = 12$ and 26% . The reduction of Racah parameters (B) from the free ion value of 1056 cm^{-1} to 933 or 786 cm^{-1} and the β^0 value of 12 and 26% indicate the covalent nature of the compounds²². The polystyrene-anchored iron(III) compounds exhibit three bands in the range : $12500\text{--}12800$, $18300\text{--}19650$ and $23800\text{--}25000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to the ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}(G)$ transitions respectively in an octahedral field²¹.

Experimental

Chloromethylated polystyrene (1.17 mmol of Cl per g of resin and 2% crosslinked with divinylbenzene), nickel(II) acetate tetrahydrate [Fluka AG (Switzerland)]; 2-aminoethanethiol hydrochloride, 2-aminothiophenol [Aldrich Chemical Co. (USA)]; sodium bicarbonate, anhydrous sodium acetate [Glaxo]; copper(II) acetate dihydrate, cadmium(II) acetate dihydrate, cobalt(II) acetate monohydrate, anhydrous iron(III) chloride, zinc(II) acetate dihydrate, uranyl acetate tetrahydrate [B.D.H.]; DMF, DMSO, ethyl acetate, acetone, benzene, diethyl ether, dioxane, CH_2Cl_2 , ethanol, methanol [Ranbaxy]; petroleum ether [I.D.P.L.] were used for the syntheses. Bis(acetylacetonato)-dioxomolybdenum(VI) was synthesized according to the published procedures²³. The metal contents, coordinated DMF, IR, reflectance spectral studies and magnetic susceptibility measurements on the polystyrene-anchored coordination compounds were carried out as per our recent publication¹⁵.

Synthesis of aldehydopolystyrene (PS-CHO) :

The title polymer was synthesized as per the published procedure²⁴. Chloromethylated polystyrene (20.0 g, 1.17 mmol Cl/g of resin), suspended in DMSO (300 ml) was stirred with NaHCO_3 (6.0 g) for 12 h at $\sim 140^\circ$. The product

obtained was suction filtered, washed with DMSO, hot water (several times) and then with dioxane- H_2O (1 : 1), dioxane, ethanol, CH_2Cl_2 and C_6H_6 . It was then dried *in vacuo* at room temperature.

Synthesis of polystyrene-anchored Schiff bases (PS-LH) (1) and PS-L'H (2) :

The aldehydopolystyrene (1.0 g) was allowed to swell in DMF (50 ml) for 45 min. A hot DMF solution (40 ml) of 2-aminoethanethiol hydrochloride (0.53 g, 4.68 mmol) was added to a hot DMF solution (20 ml) of sodium acetate (0.38 g, 4.68 mmol) and the mixture was stirred magnetically for 5 min and then cooled to room temperature. The separated sodium chloride was filtered off. The filtrate obtained was added to the above suspension of aldehydopolystyrene. For the preparation of PS-L'H (2), a hot DMF solution (50 ml) of 2-aminothiophenol (0.60 g, 4.68 mmol) was added to the above suspension of aldehydopolystyrene. The mixture was heated under reflux for 8 h, while stirring magnetically. The cream coloured products obtained were suction filtered while hot, washed with hot DMF, ethanol, methanol and diethyl ether and then dried as mentioned above.

General method for the syntheses of polystyrene-anchored coordination compounds, [PS-LM(CH₃COO)·DMF] or [PS-L'M(CH₃COO)·DMF] [where M = Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, UO₂^{VI}] and [PS-LNi(CH₃COO)·3DMF] or [PS-L'Ni(CH₃COO)·3DMF] :

1.0 g of PS-LH (1) or PS-L'H (2) was allowed to swell in DMF (40 ml) for 1 h. To this, a DMF solution (30–60 ml) of appropriate metal acetate (2.34 mmol) was added. The mixture was heated under reflux, while stirring magnetically for ~ 6 h. The mixture was cooled to room temperature and products obtained were suction filtered, washed thoroughly with DMF, ethanol and petroleum ether and were dried as mentioned above.

Synthesis of [PS-LFeCl₂·2DMF] or [PS-L'FeCl₂·2DMF] :

1.0 g of PS-LH (1) or PS-L'H (2) was allowed to swell in DMF (40 ml) for 1 h. To this, a DMF solution (60 ml) of iron(III) chloride (anhydrous) (0.38 g, 2.34 mmol) was added. The mixture was refluxed for 14 h under anhydrous conditions, while stirring magnetically. The mixture was cooled to room temperature. The red coloured products obtained were suction filtered, washed with DMF and methanol and were dried as mentioned above.

Synthesis of [PS-LCo(CH₃COO)·3DMF] or [PS-L'Co(CH₃COO)·3DMF] :

1.0 g of PS-LH (1) or PS-L'H (2) was allowed to swell

in DMF (40 ml) for 1 h. To this, a hot DMF solution (80 ml) of cobalt(II) acetate tetrahydrate (0.58 g, 2.34 mmol, flushed with N₂) was added. The mixture was heated under reflux for 8 h in nitrogen atmosphere, while stirring magnetically. The brown coloured products obtained were cooled to room temperature, suction filtered, washed with de-aerated (by passing nitrogen) DMF, ethanol and acetone and were dried as mentioned above.

Synthesis of [PS-LMoO₂(acac)] or [PS-L'MoO₂(acac)] :

1.0 g of PS-LH (1) or PS-L'H (2) was allowed to swell in DMF (40 ml) for 1 h. To this, a DMF solution (75 ml) of bis(acetylacetonato)dioxomolybdenum(VI) (0.76 g, 2.34 mmol) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 12 h, while stirring magnetically. The mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature and the pale-yellow products obtained were suction filtered, washed thoroughly with DMF, ethanol, methanol, acetone and petroleum ether and were dried as mentioned above.

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References

1. J. Topich, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1982, **21**, 2079; S. Bhaduri, H. Khawaja and V. Khanwalkar, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1982, 445; T. M. Suzuki and T. Yokoyama, *Polyhedron*, 1983, **2**, 127.
2. T. Brunelet, C. Jouitteau and G. Gelbard, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1986, **51**, 4016; A. Akelah, M. S. Masoud and S. S. Kandil, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1986, **25**, 918; C. Kantipuly, S. Katragadda, A. Chow and H. D. Gesser, *Talanta*, 1990, **37**, 491.
3. A. Syamal and M. M. Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1993, **32**, 861.
4. S. Padhye and G. B. Kauffman, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1985, **63**, 127; S. Sidhanta and H. R. Das, *Talanta*, 1987, **32**, 457.
5. P. Bogoizek and E. K. Balawejder, *Polymer*, 1985, **30**, 439; C. D. Garner, R. Durant and F. E. Mabbs, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1977, **24**, 129.
6. M. Mohan, A. Agarwal and N. Jha, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 1981, **34**, 41.
7. A. Maiti, A. K. Guha and A. Gosh, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 1988, **41**, 13.
8. H. Singh, L. D. S. Yadav and S. B. S. Mishra, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1981, **43**, 1701; N. K. Kaushik and A. K. Mishra, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2003, **42**, 2762.
9. D. Lanigan, "Proceeding of International Conference on PVC Processing", Plastic and Rubber Institute, London, 1978, 41.
10. A. G. Davies and P. J. Smith, *Adv. Inorg. Chem. Radiochem.*, 1980, **23**, 1.
11. A. Syamal and O. P. Singhal, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1981, **43**, 2821; A. Syamal and D. Kumar, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1984, **14**, 325.
12. A. Syamal, D. Kumar and S. Ahmad, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982, **21**, 634; A. Syamal and D. Kumar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1993, **32**, 625.
13. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", 3rd. ed., Wiley Interscience, New York, 1987, pp. 232, 249.
14. N. B. Colthup, L. H. Daly and S. E. Wiberley, "Introduction to Infrared and Raman Spectroscopy", 2nd. ed., Academic Press, London, 1975, pp. 284, 408.
15. D. Kumar, A. Syamal and A. K. Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2003, **42**, 280.
16. A. Syamal and M. R. Maurya, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1989, **95**, 183.
17. A. Dey, R. K. Maiti and J. K. Bhar, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1981, **6**, 346.
18. E. C. Alyea, A. Malek and A. K. Kazi, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1981, **6**, 223.
19. N. K. Singh and S. B. Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2001, **40**, 1070; B. B. Mahapatra and P. Ray, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **79**, 609.
20. D. W. Warad, C. D. Satish, V. H. Kulkarni and C. S. Bajgur, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2000, **39**, 415.
21. A. B. P. Lever, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", 2nd. ed., Elsevier, Amsterdam and references therein.
22. A. Syamal, *Chem. Educ.*, 1987, **4**, 33.
23. G. J. Chen, J. W. McDonald and W. E. Newton, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1976, **15**, 2612.
24. K. S. Devaky and V. N. R. Pillai, *Eur. Polym. J.*, 1988, **24**, 209.